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Review Article

**BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITIES OF BENZIMIDAZOLE
DERIVATIVES – A REVIEW****Purna Nagasree Kurre^{1*}, Krishnaveni Patnala¹, Thalla Srinu¹, Gunturi Surya Varchas
Varma¹, Jagadeesh Panda¹**¹Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry & Analysis, Raghu College of Pharmacy, Dakamari,
Visakhapatnam - 531162 India**Article Received: May 2024****Accepted: May 2024****Published: June 2024****Abstract:**

Over the last few decades, data on the production of benzimidazole and its derivatives, as well as an assessment of their biological activity, have been reviewed. The synthesis and development of novel compounds are discussed historically, since they are considered a significant heterocyclic moiety with a broad variety of medicinal uses. The synthesis of benzimidazoles and their derivatives continues to be a primary focus for synthetic chemistry communities due to their wide range of activities, which include anti-bacterial, anti-viral, anti-fungal, anti-diabetic, anti-helminthic, anti-convulsant, anti-HIVs, anti-hypertensive, anti-cancer, anti-inflammatory, and anti-oxidant. The goal of this study is to provide up-to-date information on the biological activities and synthesis of various benzimidazole derivatives. Additionally, we have attempted to provide an overview of the chemistry involved in the production of several benzimidazole derivatives for use in medicine.

Keywords: Benzimidazole, biological activity, synthesis.

Corresponding author:**Dr. Purna Nagasree Kurre,**

Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry & Analysis,

Raghu College of Pharmacy, Dakamari, Visakhapatnam - 531162 India

E Mail: kpurna2104@gmail.com

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

Benzimidazole, also known as 1,3-diazaindene, is a heterocyclic molecule that is made up of an imidazole ring fused with benzene. It contains sulphur, oxygen, and nitrogen, and its derivatives are highly sought-after due to its variety of biological activities and medical uses. O-phenylene diamine is one of the derivatives of benzimidazoles, which are also known as ortho phenylene [1]. Many intriguing biological activities, including those that are antimicrobial, anticancer, antifungal, anti-inflammatory, anthelmintic, antibacterial, anti-psychotic, anti-convulsant, anti-hypertensive, antidiabetic, antioxidant, and in various chemical fields, have been reported for benzimidazole and its derivatives [2].

Hoebreckee produced benzimidazole for the first time in 1872 by reducing 2-nitro-4-methyl acetanilide. These days, a lot of researchers have published several techniques for creating 1- or 1,2-substituted benzimidazole derivatives under various atmospheric conditions utilising various moieties. The primary process for creating mono substituted benzimidazoles (MSBs) and di substituted benzimidazoles (DSBs) involves condensation of O-phenylenediamine with an aromatic or aliphatic benzaldehyde ketonic group, utilising various solvent and catalyst conditions that are outlined below. The best yield is obtained using novel techniques; nonetheless, bulky groups replaced with aldehyde exhibit poor yield [3]. The tautomerization of the H-atom between double and single bonded nitrogen atoms in the planar benzimidazole ring is demonstrated in figure 1[4]. This results in chemically equivalent tautomer's, which can be expressed as two sets of numbers to indicate the positions of the substituent group, such as 5-methylbenzimidazole (1) or 6-methylbenzimidazole (2). A number of previous attempts have been made to develop a low-cost, effective method for the synthesis of derivatives of benzimidazoles. The first of the three primary procedures is the Weidenhagen reaction, which is based on the interaction of ortho-phenylenediamine with aldehydes and ketones. The second technique is the Phillips-Ladenburg reaction, which is based on the association of diaminobenzenes with carboxylic acids and their derivatives. The third process is called Mamedov heterocyclic rearrangement, and it involves converting a quinoxalinone derivative into 2-heterocyclic-substituted benzimidazoles with the help of an acid [5].

Figure 1: Tautomer's of benzimidazole moiety [4].

One crucial pharmacophore in contemporary drug research is the benzimidazole ring. Recently, there has been a greater focus on the synthesis of derivatives of benzimidazoles. An ongoing area of great interest in medicine is the production of new benzimidazole derivatives. Benzimidazoles are classified as two-ring aromatic systems and hold a key place in the pharmaceutical business nowadays. N-alkylation (1-substitution) and 2-substitution introduced into benzimidazoles have strong effects in the pharmaceutical industry. In order to find different absorbing drugs, benzimidazole is a structurally diverse ligand that can bind to different receptor sites [6].

Benzimidazole derivatives can bind to the microtubules to stop the growth of hyphae in fungi. Carbendazim is used as an anti-fungicide [7]. Methyl-2-benzimidazole carbamate is an anti-cancer agent that can reduce the apoptosis of cancer cells [8]. Benzimidazole derivatives are also used in hypertension and as tyrosine kinase inhibitors. Mibefradil is used as an anti-hypertensive drug [9]. Benzimidazole derivatives also have the property meiotic arrest act as anti-cancer and can block nuclear division by binding with the spindle microtubules. Proton pump inhibitors such as omeprazole and rabeprazole are used to treat gastric ulcers [10], 2-mercapito benzimidazole derivatives have anti-convulsant activity [11], mebendazole is used to treat parasitosis, bis-benzimidazole derivative is cytotoxic against breast adenocarcinoma and also active in skin epidermoid carcinoma [12], and envirodine acts as an anti-viral [13]. Certain benzimidazole derivatives, such as 5-chloro and 5,6 di chloro-substituted derivatives, exhibit specific activity against a number of viruses, including cytomegalovirus, influenza, hepatitis B virus, hepatitis C, and HIV-1, among others. A large number of molecules based on benzimidazole have varying pharmaceutical importance, some of which are FDA-approved drugs.

Figure 2. Importance of benzimidazole in different pharmaceutical fields

This perspective holds that in order to comprehend the current status of different benzimidazole nuclei in organic and medicinal chemistry research, it is necessary to draw links between the data presented in the most recent literature and the literature from earlier periods. In this work, an attempt has been made to shed light on the most recent understanding of the synthesis and use of numerous benzimidazole derivatives. We have also tried to present a general review of the chemistry involved in the synthesis of a number of medicinally useful benzimidazole derivatives.

1. Synthesis of the benzimidazole core molecule:

Historical records state that in 1872, Hoebrecker reduced 2-nitro-4-methyl acetanilide to create the first benzimidazole derivatives, 2,5 and 2,6-dimethyl benzimidazole [14].

Scheme 1: Preparation of benzimidazole from 2-nitro-4-methylacetanilide.

The synthesis of two-substituted benzimidazoles can be accomplished in three main ways: first, through the Weidenhagen reaction, which is based on the interaction of ortho-phenylenediamine with aldehydes and ketones; second, through the Phillips-Landerburg reaction, which is based on the relationship between diaminobenzenes and derivatives of carboxylic acids; and third, through a process known as Mamedov heterocyclic rearrangement, which is referred to as Mamedov heterocyclic rearrangement and involves converting quinoxalinone derivatives into 2-heteroaryl-substituted benzimidazole under the influence of an acid.

2. Phillips-Ladenburg reaction in Benzimidazole synthesis:

According to studies, a variety of benzimidazole derivatives can be made by combining carboxylic acids and o-phenylenediamine. By condensing o-phenylenediamine and aromatic acid (salicylic acid, benzoic acid, cinnamic acid, etc.) at 80°C–90°C with ammonium chloride (NH₄Cl) acting as a catalyst in EtOH, benzimidazole derivatives may be generated in a 72%–90% yield [15].

Scheme 2: Benzimidazole preparation from carboxylic acids

3. Weidenhagen reaction in Benzimidazole synthesis:

Excellent yields of benzimidazole compounds are obtained by condensing *o*-phenylenediamine with an aldehyde at room temperature in methanol conditions for six hours in an open oxygen environment using $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$ as a catalyst [16].

Scheme 3: Preparation of benzimidazole from aldehyde

4. Mamedov heterocyclic rearrangement in Benzimidazole synthesis:

Benzimidazole derivatives are created via the rearrangement of quinoxalinones when 4,5-diamino-6-hydroxy-2-mercaptopyrimidine and alkanoyl(aryl)quinoxalin-2(1H)-ones are refluxed for six hours in *n*-butanol(*n*-BuOH) with H_2SO_4 present [17].

Scheme 4: Synthesis of benzimidazole derivatives from alkanoyl(aryl)quinoxalin-2(1H)-ones

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Benzimidazole as antiprotozoal agents:

For the purpose of researching the antiprotozoal activity of 5-substituted 4,6-dibromo-2-mercapto benzimidazole derivatives, novel compounds were created. The synthetic compounds shown efficacy in combating *Giardia intestinalis*.

Compound 1:

By using the bis-O-acetoxyamidoxime to create a series of biphenyl benzimidazole diamidines from their corresponding diamidoximes, Ismail et al. hydrogenated the compounds in ethanol and glacial acetic acid with Pd acting as a catalyst. They then assessed the compounds antiprotozoal activity against *Plasmodium falciparum*. Excellent yield was shown by the synthesised compound -(4-amidino-4-hydroxybiphenyl-3-yl)-1H-benzimidazole-5-amidine acetate ^[18].

2-(4'-carbamimidoyl-4-hydroxy-[1,1'-biphenyl]-3-yl)-1H-benzo[d]imidazole-5-carboximidamide

Figure 3: compound -1

Compound 2 :

When 5-substituted 4,6-dibromo-2-mercapto benzimidazole derivatives were synthesised, Andrzejewska et al. reported that the newly synthesised drugs were many times more potent against *Giardia intestinalis* ^[19].

Figure 4: Compound-2

Benzimidazole as anthelmintic agents :**Compound 3 :**

The treatment of parasitic illnesses involved the use of many benzimidazole compounds. To increase their anti-helminthic action against *Trichinella spiralis*, Mavrova et al. synthesised 5-(6)-(un)substituted-1H-benzimidazole-2-yl thioacetyl piperazine derivatives. It is clear from the aforementioned study that the most active one is 2-(2-{2-[4-(4-chlorophenyl) piperazin-1-yl]-2-oxoethyl} thio)-5(6)-methyl-1H-benzimidazole ^[20].

1-(4-(4-chlorophenyl)piperazin-1-yl)-2-((6-methyl-1H-benzo[d]imidazol-2-yl)thio)ethan-1-one

Figure 5: Compound-3

Compound 4 :

Some novel Valero lactone derivatives of 5(6)-substituted-(1H-benzimidazole-2-yl-amine) have been synthesised by Beatriz et al. The anti-helminthic activity of each chemical against the *N. Brasilensis species* was tested. It has been discovered that several of the synthesised chemicals have excellent activities [21].

Figure 6: Compound-4**Benzimidazole as antibacterial agents:****Compound 5:**

The broad range antibacterial activity of 2-piperidin-4-yl-benzimidazoles was evaluated by He and colleagues against a variety of species of microbes, including *Enterococcus*, *C. albicans*, and *P. Aeruginosa*. Compound N1[4-(5,6-dichloro-2-piperidin-4-yl-benzimidazol-1-ylmethyl)-NT was discovered from the aforementioned investigation [22].

*N*¹-(4-((5,6-dichloro-2-(piperidin-4-yl)-1*H*-benzo[*d*]imidazol-1-yl)methyl)benzyl)ethane-1,2-diamine**Figure 7:** Compound 5**Compound 6:**

Novel 2-(6-fluorochroman-2-yl)-1-alkyl/acyl/aroil-1-*H*benzimidazole derivatives were synthesised by Kumar et al. and tested against various antibacterial agents. A few of the compounds that were synthesised shown encouraging antibacterial action against *Salmonella typhimurium* [23].

Figure 8: Compound-6

Benzimidazole as Anti-HIV agents:**Compound 7:**

Using naphthamidines and 2-aminobenzimidazoles, Middleton et al. synthesised HIV type 1 integrase inhibitors and discovered that the aforementioned chemical emerged as a powerful integrase inhibitor [24].

5-methyl-1H-benzimidazole-2,7-diamine

Figure 9: Compound-7**Benzimidazole as Antifungal agents:****Compound 8:**

Numerous derivatives of benzimidazole, including 2-substituted phenyl-1H-(5-substituted) benzimidazole, were synthesised and assessed for their ability to inhibit *Candida species*. Antimicrobial study results indicate that cyano-substituted compounds have excellent action, particularly 1-butyl-2-(4-fluoro-phenyl)-1H-benzimidazole-5-carbonitrile [25].

1-butyl-2-(4-fluorophenyl)-1H-benzimidazole-5-carbonitrile

Figure 10: Compound-8**Compound 9:**

Kawasaki and colleagues created new benzofuran compounds that target the fungus N-myristoyl transferase in order to act as antifungal drugs. In a mouse systemic candidiasis model, benzimidazole derivative (1-allyl-1H-benzimidazol-2-yl)-[4-(3-benzylamino-propoxy)-3-methyl-benzofuran-2-yl]-methanone shown strong antifungal activity [26].

(1-allyl-1H-benzimidazol-2-yl)-[4-(3-benzylamino)propoxy]-3-methylbenzofuran-2-ylmethanone

Figure 11: Compound-9**Benzimidazoles as Anticancer agents:**

Since cancer is a malignant illness marked by unchecked cell growth, several anti-cancer medications are presently being used. Medicinal chemists have recently become interested in studying the potential of benzimidazole derivatives as anticancer medicines.

Compound 10:

In their investigation, Ramla et al. synthesised 3-(2-methyl-1H-benzimidazol-5-ylimino) and 2-(1-benzyl-2-methyl-1H-benzimidazol-5-ylimino)-3-(substituted)-thiazolidines-4-ones. Investigated the anti-tumour potential of 2-substituted thiazolidines-4-ones against the activation of the Epstein-Barr virus early antigen (EBV-EA) caused by 12-O-tetradecanoyl phorbol-13-acetate. The findings demonstrated the substantial activity of 3-benzoyl-2-(1-benzyl-2-methyl-1H-benzimidazol-5-yl-imino) thiazolidin-4-one [27].

(Z)-3-benzoyl-2-((1-benzyl-2-methyl-1H-benzo[d]imidazol-5-yl)imino)thiazolidin-4-one**Figure 12:** Compound-10**Compound 11:**

A few new benzimidazole derivatives have been developed and synthesised by Jin et al., and they have been tested on human tumour cell lines. The majority of compounds have an anti-proliferation impact on tumour cell lines that are solid. The immune-fluorescence approach was used to assess the compound's cellular activity [28].

6-methyl-2-(methylsulfonyl)-N-(3-(5-(morpholinomethyl)-1H-benzo[d]imidazol-2-yl)-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)pyrimidin-4-amine**Figure 13:** Compound -11

Benzimidazole as antidiabetic agent:**Compound 12:**

By activating PPAR-mediated transcriptional activity, the series of 3-(2,4-dichlorobenzyl)-2-methyl-N-(pentylsulphoyl)-3H-benzimidazole-5-carboxamide (FK614) that Minoura et al. synthesised improves insulin resistance in C57BL/KSJ-db/db mice (db/db mice) animal models, making it a novel therapeutic candidate for the treatment of type-2 diabetic patients ^[29].

1-(2,4-dichlorobenzyl)-2-methyl-N-(pentylsulfonyl)-1H-benzo[d]imidazole-6-carboxamide

Figure 14: Compound- 12

Benzimidazole as anti-inflammatory agents:**Compound 13:**

Several new compounds of 2-substituted benzimidazoles were synthesised by Radha et al. The carrageenan-induced hind paw edema technique was utilised to test the synthesised compounds for their potential anti-inflammatory properties. Fluoro and chloro substituents (R) in combination with the studied drugs showed excellent selectivity in the suppression of inflammation ^[30].

Figure 15: Compound-13

Compound 14:

After creating a number of imidazolyl benzimidazoles, Mader et al. discovered that only a small number of them were effective p38 MAP kinase inhibitors. In the pathophysiology of both acute and chronic inflammatory reactions, P38 is a key player. P38 is activated in monocytes and macrophages in response to several stress-related stimuli ^[31].

Figure 16: Compound-14

Benzimidazole as antiviral agent:**Compound 15:**

Some new benzimidazoles have been successfully synthesised by Cheng et al. (Compound 14). The majority of these substances exhibited strong selective action when tested for antiviral activity against *Coxsackie virus B3* in VERO cells^[32].

(R₁= 2- pyridyl, 1-benzyl, 2-fluorobenzyl)

Figure 17: Compound-15

Compound 16:

Clercq and Naesens synthesised many nucleoside and non-nucleoside analogues of benzimidazoles as part of their hunt for potent anti-HHV-6 medicines. It was discovered that 2-bromo-5,6-dichlorobenzimidazole was the active analogue in non-nucleoside analogues^[33].

2-bromo-5,6-dichloro-1H-benzo[d]imidazole

Figure 18: Compound- 16

Benzimidazole as anti-microbial agents:**Compound 17:**

In order to synthesise the 5(6)-bromo-1-[(phenyl)sulfonyl], Zhang et al.-2- [methyl (4-nitrophenoxy)] tested the antibacterial activity of -1H-benzimidazoles against *S. aureus*, *Micrococcus luteus*, *Bacillus subtilis*, and *Bacillus proteus*. Good antibacterial activity was demonstrated by the compounds^[34].

N-((1*H*-benzo[*d*]imidazol-2-yl)methyl)-*N*-ethyl-4-methylaniline

Figure 19: Compound -17

Compound 18:

The antibacterial properties of a few new 2-substituted-1-[(5-substituted alkyl/aryl)-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl]methyl derivatives. Ansari et al. observed that majority of the derivatives of -1*H*-benzimidazole showed action against the tested strains of fungus and bacteria ^[35].

(R=H, -CH₃; R₁= -CH₃, -C₂H₅, 4-ClC₆H₄,
4-OHC₆H₄, 4-OHCH₃C₆H₄)

Figure 20: Compound-18

Benzimidazole as antioxidant agents:

Compound 19:

Hideg and colleagues have produced an array of 4-carboxyamidobenzimidazoles. By using electron paramagnetic resonance (EPR) technology, the antioxidant activity of these new compounds has been assessed for benzimidazole hydroxyl radical scavenging. These substances exhibited strong PARP inhibitor scavenging activity ^[36].

2-(2,2,6,6-tetramethyl-1,2,3,6-tetrahydropyridin-4-yl)-1*H*-benzo[*d*]imidazole-4-carboxamide

Figure 21: Compound -19

CONCLUSION:

According to the previously mentioned research, benzimidazole is a flexible heterocyclic nucleus with the ability to create novel chemical compounds. The synthesis processes for benzimidazole and its derivatives are identified chemically. Because benzimidazole and its derivatives have so many pharmacological uses, there is a high need for new synthesis methods. Additionally, we have made an effort to discuss the significant biological activities of benzimidazole derivatives, including their potential for treating a variety of illnesses, including HIV, cancer, diabetes, inflammatory diseases, viruses, bacterial. They also have antioxidant properties.

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